

Achievement Motivation and its Relation to the Role of Extra – Curricular Activities in the Development of Creative Thinking Skills Through the Perspective of Students in the Governmental Schools in Al – Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan

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Abstract

The study aimed at measuring the level of "achievement motivation and its relation to the role of extra – curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills through the perspective of students at the governmental schools in Al – Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan". The results showed statistically significant differences due to the impact of gender in all domains except for the domain of success emitting value and the difference came in favor of the females, the non – existence of statistically significant differences due to the effect of educational stage in all domains except for the domain of the motive to success where the differences came in favor of the ninth grade, and the absence of statistically significant differences due to the interaction between gender and educational stage in all domains.

1. Introduction

Studying the various motivations helps the individual in understanding his own self and others. They introduce us to the motives that motivate individuals to perform different behaviors in different situations and circumstances. They can be identified as the available possibilities in the surrounding environment of an individual used to stimulate more of his motivations toward a specific behavior and to perform a specific activity or activities in a way that fulfil his desire and needs.

They enable us to explain others behavior in certain situations and help us predict human's behavior in a given situation and know the individual's motivations. They can be used to direct one's behavior in a specific direction; the teacher's motivation to work appears in his conduct with his students in the class management and his impact on the students, as for the teacher's impact is not limited to the subject he teaches rather than it is related to his tendencies, values, habits and behavior which quickly are transferred to his students for he is an example and a role model to be followed. The teacher is the students' ideal in morals, achievements, behavior ...etc. A teacher might be excellent in the subject related to his specialty but might lack the ability to explain this subject to the students in an understandable comprehensive way, therefor; the teacher of gifted students must enjoy a motivation, the scientific achievement motivation, to help students through the educational situations (Al-wadi, 2012).

Thus, it is clear that all types of school activities contribute significantly to the development of students' personalities and their moral, social, psychological, physical and mental education, which prepare them for future life situations and have a significant impact on the education of learners that exceeds education in classrooms (Arafa, 2010).

Thinking in all its types is the core of attention of educational institutions. Creative thinking currently receives great attention from planners and experts for its development in order to benefit from it. Developed countries seek developing the students' creative skills through all the available means (Duwaidi, 2008). Creative thinking is "a complex purposeful mental activity driven by a strong desire to look for solutions or original results that were not known before. Creative thinking is characterized by comprehensiveness and complexity as it implies interconnected emotional and moral elements forming a unique mental state (Jirwan, 2004).

In this regard, Duwaidi (2008) stated that there is concordance among many educators on the importance of motivating the students' creativity, its development and its training in different methods. In United States there are more than thirty methods for creativity training, in Japan there are more than a hundred; including the American methods, aiming at qualifying the minds to be thoughtful, creative, and able to solve the varied and complicated problems of life in unconventional ways.

Methodology of the study:

The study approach: the approach that was followed in this study is the descriptive correlational approach that one of its types is the scientific research. It is considered as the most important approach followed in this type of studies as it is characterized by accuracy in illustrating the reality of scientific phenomena and the factors that lead to commit it.

Population and sample of the study:

The population of the study included all students in Karak governorate's schools. (2) Schools have been chosen (AL-Shihabiya Secondary School for boys and Al-Shihabiya Secondary Mixed School for girls). The study used the simple random sample method as for the targeted category is school students. The sample composed of (94) students; males and females, (45) of them are males and (49) are females. Table (1) explains this:

Table (1): repetitions and percentages according to the variables of the study

		Categories	Repetitions	Percentage
Gender		Male	45	47.9
		Female	49	52.1
Educational stage		Ninth grade	44	46.8
		Tenth grade	50	53.2
		Total	94	100.0

		Educational stage		Total
		Ninth grade	Tenth grade	
Gender	Male	20	25	45
	Female	24	25	49
Total		44	50	94

Variables of the study:

Independent variables: gender, educational stage.

Dependent variables: achievement motivation, extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills.

Tools of the study:

1- The tool of achievement motivation:

The researcher used Al-Sahli scale (2015) for achievement motivation, composed of (4) domains; each domain is composed of (6) items. The domains are (motive to success domain, success probability domain, success emitting value domain, cognitive motivation and achievement domain).

Table (2): dimensions of achievement motivation scale, the number of items for each and their responses

No.	dimension (skill)	Domain referring items					
		1	motive to success	1	5	9	13
2	Success probability	2	6	10	14	18	22
3	Success emitting value	3	7	11	15	19	23
4	Cognitive motivation and achievement	4	8	12	16	20	24
	Total	1 – 24					

The answers of the scale's items vary from (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never), respectively given the following degrees (5 – 4 – 3 – 2 – 1) for all the items.

Validity of the original scale:

Validity has been verified through two ways:

A- Content validity:

This scale has been developed depending on particular procedural steps, referring to previous literature, the theoretical framework, and the content of the available scales that indicate the achievement motivation. These procedures were considered the proof of the content validity.

B- External validity:

The test has been reviewed by ten specialized arbitrators to judge the appropriateness of its items to the students, their clarity, their efficiency, the sufficiency of their numbers, and their illustration of achievement motivation that all these items have been developed to measure it. Arbitrators notes have been taken into account and the required modifications have been applied as four items have been deleted. (85%) of the arbitrators' agreement has been adopted.

Reliability of the original scale:

Reliability of the achievement motivation scale has been verified through the (test-retest) method. The scale has been repeated two weeks later on an external group, separated from the study sample, composed of (40) students. Pearson correlation coefficient has been calculated for both times and it ranged between (0.71 – 0.76). The internal consistency coefficient was calculating based on Cronbach's Alpha formula. It varied between (0.62 – 0.92). Table (3) shows the internal consistency coefficient according to Cronbach's Alpha formula and

the reliability of repetition for the domains and the tool as a whole. These values were considered appropriate for the objectives of this study. Table (3) explains this:

Table (3): Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient and the reliability of repetition for the achievement motivation scale

No.	Domain	Reliability of repetition	Internal consistency
1)	Motive to success	0.74	0.86
2)	Success probability	0.76	0.92
3)	Success emitting value	0.72	0.62
4)	Cognitive motivation and achievement	0.71	0.69
	Achievement motivation scale as a whole	0.73	0.77

2- The tool of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills:

The researcher used Al-Yami scale (2014), composed of (41) items. The researcher has developed the study tool addressed to the students. (41) Items divided over (5) domains: first domain is fluency composed of (9) items, the second is flexibility composed of (8) items, the third is originality composed of (8) items, the fourth is details composed of (8) items and the fifth is problems sensitivity composed of (8) items.

Validity of the original scale:

First: the validity of arbitrators: The scale has been reviewed by ten specialized arbitrators in educational psychology and educational sciences in Al-Balqa' Applied University. Base on their notes, some words and structures have been changed. 80% of the arbitrators' agreement has been adopted.

Second: construct validity: correlation coefficients between the items and the dimension have been calculated and their total score. Table (4) explains this:

Table (4): correlation coefficients between the items and the dimensions, and the total score of the study tool

Item no.	Dimension	Total score	Item no.	Dimension	Total score	Item no.	Dimension	Total score
1	.618**	.487**	15	.737**	.657**	29	.773**	.644**
2	.676**	.504**	16	.667**	.599**	30	.777**	.668**
3	.630**	.465**	17	.745**	.692**	31	.752**	.682**
4	.634**	.524**	18	.695**	.666**	32	.808**	.700**
5	.647**	.590**	19	.710**	.631**	33	.744**	.664**
6	.710**	.584**	20	.707**	.654**	34	.657**	.633**
7	.731**	.600**	21	.653**	.594**	35	.638**	.578**
8	.640**	.471**	22	.757**	.681**	36	.755**	.628**
9	.599**	.521**	23	.715**	.660**	37	.730**	.613**
10	.689**	.573**	24	.689**	.547**	38	.744**	.709**
11	.683**	.541**	25	.640**	.595**	39	.717**	.646**
12	.708**	.611**	26	.677**	.667**	40	.727**	.603**
13	.599**	.478**	27	.677**	.612**	41	.719**	.616**
14	.619**	.593**	28	.694**	.549**			

From the above table we see that correlation coefficients are statistically significant at ($\alpha=0.05$) and are accepted for the objectives of the study.

Reliability of the original scale: The reliability of the scale has been verified through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. It was calculated as an indicator of internal consistency. The following table clarifies Cronbach's Alpha coefficients. The study tool has been applied to verify its validity and reliability over a survey sample from outside the study sample (30) students; males and females. Table (5) clarifies this:

Table (5): Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the study tool and its sub-dimensions

Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha coefficient
Fluency	0.83
Flexibility	0.84
Originality	0.85
Details	0.88
Problem sensitivity	0.88
Total	0.96

Explanation of the degrees on the scale:

The process of correcting the scale was conducted through viewing the students' answers that were given according to Likert Scale with the following order (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never) and give each the following values respectively (5, 4, 3, 2, 1). To evaluate the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills, the following coefficient has been followed:

- The arithmetic mean of the item that is less than 2.33 represents a low role.

- The arithmetic mean of the item that ranges from 2.33 to 3.66 represents a medium role.
- The arithmetic mean of the item that ranges from 3.67 to 5 represents a high role.

Presenting the results related to the questions of the study and their discussion:

First question: What is the level of achievement motivation among students in governmental schools in Karak city in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and the standard deviations have been calculated for the level of achievement motivation among governmental schools students in Karak city in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

Table (6): A .M and S.D of the level of achievement motivation among governmental schools students in Karak city of Jordan

Rank	No.	Domain	A.M	S.D	Level
1	1	Motive to success	4.25	.559	High
2	2	Success probability	4.00	.613	High
3	3	Success emitting value	3.96	.628	High
4	4	Cognitive motivation and achievement	3.79	.693	High
		Achievement motivation as a whole	4.00	.466	High

Table (6) shows that arithmetic means have ranged from (3.79 to 4.25). The domain of motive to success came in the first rank with the highest arithmetic mean (4.25), whereas the domain of cognitive motivation and achievement came in the last rank with an arithmetic mean of (3.79). The arithmetic mean of achievement motivation as a whole was (4.00).

Second question: What is the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills from the perspective of governmental schools students in Karak city in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan? To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations have been calculated for the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills from the perspective of governmental schools students in Karak city in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. The following table shows this:

Table (7)

Rank	No.	Skill	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Level
	2	Flexibility	4.20	.572	High
	1	Fluency	4.19	.480	High
	4	Details	4.12	.622	High
	3	Originality	4.00	.617	High
	5	Problem sensitivity	3.94	.691	High
		Extra-curricular activities	4.09	.492	High

Table (5) shows that arithmetic means have ranged from (3.94 to 4.20). The skill of flexibility came in the first rank with the highest arithmetic mean (4.20), whereas the skill of problem sensitivity came in the last rank with an arithmetic mean of (3.94). The arithmetic mean of extra-curricular activities as a whole was (4.09).

Third question: are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the level of achievement motivation in governmental schools in Karak city in the Hashemite kingdom of Jordan attributed to the variables of gender and educational stage and the interaction between the two?

To answer this question, arithmetic means and standard deviations have been calculated for the level of achievement motivation in the governmental schools in Karak city in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan according to the variables of gender and the educational stage. Table (8) shows this:

Table (8)

	Educational stage	Male		Female		Total	
		Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Motive to success	Ninth grade	4.21	.592	4.53	.465	4.38	.545
	Tenth grade	4.07	.583	4.21	.522	4.14	.553
	Total	4.13	.585	4.37	.515	4.25	.559
Success probability	Ninth grade	3.88	.673	4.18	.491	4.05	.593
	Tenth grade	3.81	.619	4.11	.625	3.96	.633
	Total	3.84	.637	4.14	.559	4.00	.613
Success emitting value	Ninth grade	3.86	.720	4.16	.628	4.02	.681
	Tenth grade	3.99	.634	3.82	.516	3.91	.578
	Total	3.93	.669	3.99	.593	3.96	.628
Cognitive motivation and achievement	Ninth grade	3.82	.804	4.03	.673	3.93	.734
	Tenth grade	3.44	.636	3.88	.562	3.66	.634
	Total	3.61	.732	3.95	.617	3.79	.693

Achievement motivation as a whole	Ninth grade	3.94	.554	4.22	.440	4.10	.509
	Tenth grade	3.83	.405	4.01	.406	3.92	.411
	Total	3.88	.475	4.11	.433	4.00	.466

the Tow-Way Analysis has been applied on the tool as a whole; table (9):

Table (9): Two-Way Analysis of variance for the effect of gender and educational stage and the interaction between them regarding the total score of achievement motivation

Variable	Squares sum	DF	Square mean	F	Sig.
Gender	1.227	1	1.227	6.079	0.016
Educational stage	0.643	1	.643	3.187	0.078
Gender X educational stage	0.065	1	0.065	0.322	0.572
Error	18.166	90	0.202		
Total	20.175	93			

Table (10) shows the following:

- There are statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) attributed to the effect of gender. F value was (0.016). Differences were in favor of females.
- There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) attributed to the effect of educational stage. F value was (3.187) with a statistical significance of (0.078).
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- There are no statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) attributed to the effect of the interaction between gender and the educational stage. F value was (0.322) with a statistical significance of (0.572).

Forth question: Are there Are there statistically significant differences at ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) in the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills from the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan attributed to the variables of gender and the educational stage and the interaction between the two?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills from the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan according to the variables of gender and the educational stage. Table (10) explains this:

Table (10): Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills from the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan according to the variables of gender and the educational stage

	Edu.stage	Male		Female		Total	
		AM	SD	AM	SD	AM	SD
Fluency	Ninth grade	4.08	.500	4.28	.551	4.19	.532
	Tenth grade	4.18	.436	4.19	.443	4.18	.435
	Total	4.13	.463	4.24	.496	4.19	.480
Flexibility	Ninth grade	4.06	.708	4.29	.487	4.19	.601
	Tenth grade	4.19	.633	4.22	.467	4.20	.551
	Total	4.13	.663	4.26	.473	4.20	.572
Originality	Ninth grade	3.84	.668	4.09	.663	3.97	.669
	Tenth grade	3.93	.596	4.12	.544	4.02	.573
	Total	3.89	.623	4.10	.599	4.00	.617
Details	Ninth grade	4.09	.674	4.23	.682	4.17	.674
	Tenth grade	3.96	.581	4.18	.559	4.07	.575
	Total	4.02	.620	4.21	.616	4.12	.622
Problem sensitivity	Ninth grade	4.04	.578	4.01	.693	4.02	.636
	Tenth grade	3.69	.767	4.04	.668	3.87	.734
	Total	3.84	.704	4.03	.674	3.94	.691
Extra-curricular activities as a whole	Ninth grade	4.02	.528	4.18	.531	4.11	.530
	Tenth grade	3.99	.451	4.15	.467	4.07	.461
	Total	4.01	.481	4.17	.494	4.09	.492

Table (12): Multiple Tow-Way Analysis for the effect of gender and educational stage and the interaction between them regarding the skills

Variable	Domains	Squares sum	DF	Square mean	F	Sig.
Gender Hotelling= .038 $\eta^2 = .663$	Fluency	.277	1	.277	1.186	.279
	Flexibility	.391	1	.391	1.180	.280
	Originality	1.159	1	1.159	3.048	.084
	Details	.763	1	.763	1.965	.164
	Problem sensitivity	.607	1	.607	1.294	.258
Educational stage Hotelling= .048 $\eta^2 = .540$	Fluency	.000	1	.000	.002	.965
	Flexibility	.018	1	.018	.055	.815
	Originality	.082	1	.082	.217	.643
	Details	.182	1	.182	.469	.495
	Problem sensitivity	.589	1	.589	1.254	.266
Gender X educational stage Hotelling= .938 $\eta^2 = .349$	Fluency	.213	1	.213	.913	.342
	Flexibility	.231	1	.231	.697	.406
	Originality	.018	1	.018	.048	.827
	Details	.027	1	.027	.070	.792
	Problem sensitivity	.828	1	.828	1.765	.187
Error	Fluency	21.002	90	.233		
	Flexibility	29.830	90	.331		
	Originality	34.221	90	.380		
	Details	34.938	90	.388		
	Problem sensitivity	42.246	90	.469		
Total	Fluency	21.462	93			
	Flexibility	30.422	93			
	Originality	35.438	93			
	Details	35.963	93			
	Problem sensitivity	44.367	93			

Table (11): Multiple Tow-Way Analysis for the effect of gender and educational stage and the interaction between them regarding the total score of extra-curricular activities

Variable	Squares sum	DF	Square mean	F	Sig.
Gender	.593	1	.593	2.438	.122
Educational stage	.021	1	.021	.088	.768
Gender X educational stage	.000	1	.000	.001	.981
Error	21.891	90	.243		
Total	22.519	93			

Fifth question: Is there a statistically significant correlation at ($\alpha \leq 0.5$) between the achievement motivation and the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills through the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

To answer this question, Pearson correlation coefficient has been calculated between achievement motivation and the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills through the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. Table (14) explains this:

Table (12): Pearson correlation coefficient of the relationship between achievement motivation and the role of extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills through the perspective of students in the governmental schools in Al-Karak City in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan

		Motive to success	Success possibilities	Success emitting value	Cognitive motivation and achievement	Achievement motivation as a whole
Fluency	Correlation coefficient (R)	.084	-.082	-.110	.075	-.011
	Statistical significance	.420	.429	.290	.471	.916
	Number	94	94	94	94	94
Flexibility	Correlation coefficient (R)	.036	-.049	-.157	-.103	-.097
	Statistical significance	.728	.638	.130	.321	.353
	Number	94	94	94	94	94

Originality	Correlation coefficient (R)	.026	-.052	**-.271	-.146	-.155
	Statistical significance	.804	.618	.008	.160	.136
	Number	94	94	94	94	94
Details	Correlation coefficient (R)	-.051	-.125	-.186	-.096	-.155
	Statistical significance	.622	.229	.072	.360	.136
	Number	94	94	94	94	94
Problem sensitivity	Correlation coefficient (R)	.043	.021	-.021	.030	.024
	Statistical significance	.677	.840	.844	.777	.818
	Number	94	94	94	94	94
Extra-curricular activities	Correlation coefficient (R)	.032	-.067	-.177	-.059	-.094
	Statistical significance	.761	.523	.087	.575	.368
	Number	94	94	94	94	94

* Statistically significant at Sig. (0.05). ** Statistically significant at Sig. (0.01).

Discussion of the study results and recommendations:

Results :

The results showed statistically significant differences due to the impact of gender in all domains except for the domain of success emitting value and the difference came in favor of the females, the non – existence of statistically significant differences due to the effect of educational stage in all domains except for the domain of the motive to success where the differences came in favor of the ninth grade, and the absence of statistically significant differences due to the interaction between gender and educational stage in all domains.

Recommendations:

In the light of the previous results, the following recommendations were concluded:

1. The importance of the diversity of creative thinking methods in the development of extra-curricular activities, taking into account focusing on the achievement motivation of students.
2. The importance of teachers' application of creative thinking skills, achievement motivation and the students' skills according to their personal skills.
3. The importance to benefit from the nature of different extra-curricular activities in the development of creative thinking skills, the students' achievement motivation and their training.
4. Conducting studies and researches in the field of achievement motivation and creative thinking skills in the light of other variables.

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